

FOREIGN OBJECT IMPACT DAMAGE SIMULATION OF TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Aircraft landing gear components generally occupy about 4% of the entire weight of aircraft, although they are not used during the flight. Current landing gear structures are mainly made of high strength steel (e.g. 300M [1]). Corrosion and fatigue problems of such materials may occur in service, which result in increase in cost and labor to control the manufacturing quality and maintenance program. Therefore, new types of landing gear structures are demanded to avoid the above-mentioned problems.

One of the feasible candidate to replace high strength steel is carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) composite with high specific stiffness and strength. Our preliminary study [2] indicates that application of CFRP to landing gear results in increase of the volume of landing gear components, which may induce the weight of the total aircraft. In addition, very thick CFRPs are required for landing gear components, and low bearing strength and inspection problem are to be solved for the real application. This means that CFRP components are not generally suitable for landing gear structures except for the large aircraft. Light-weight but compact landing gear components are to be developed.

In this paper, application of titanium matrix composites (TMC) is considered as an alternative candidate material to solve the volume, the corrosion and the fatigue problem of landing gear structures. Prototype of TMC side stay structure, in which SiC fiber and titanium matrix were used, is shown in Fig. 1. Landing gear structures are possibly subject to foreign object impacts (e.g. stones on the ground, tools and bolts, etc.), and damage tolerant consideration is required [3]. In addition, virtual testing technology is necessary to avoid the cost/labor increase in the design and the assessment

procedures. This paper describes the experimental investigation of damage development of TMC composites subjected to foreign object impact, followed by the development of numerical simulation method. Plastic deformation and damage modeling of TMC composites are incorporated in the finite element analysis, and foreign object impact damages are simulated in this paper.

Fig. 1 TMC side stay with 800 mm length

2 Experiment

In the present study, SiC fiber/titanium matrix unidirectional composites are of interest for landing gear application. This is because landing gear structures are mainly subject to uniaxial compression and tension, and titanium matrix is

considered to be enough stiff to maintain the stability against the compression. Several kinds of TMC plates are prepared to investigate the basic mechanical properties and the damage behavior under transverse impact loads. The followings sections describe the material used, mechanical tests for basic mechanical properties, and low-velocity impact tests of TMC composites.

2.1 Material

SiC fiber/titanium matrix (Ti-3Al-2.5V) composites were fabricated using HIP(Hot Isostatic Pressing) process. In order to improve the damage resistance property, TMC composites covered by titanium (Ti-6Al-4V) clad layers were also fabricated. The resultant thickness of TMC plates was about 3mm for TMCs without clad layer, and about 3.8mm for TMCs with clad layers. The SiC fiber diameter was 100-140 μm , and the fiber volume fraction of TMC was about 33%. Cross-sectional image of the prepared TMC plate with clad layers is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Cross-sectional view of TMC with clad layer

2.2 Mechanical Properties

Basic mechanical properties were evaluated by the following mechanical tests.

- Tensile test of TMC in 0-degree direction
- Tensile test of TMC in 90-degree direction
- Tensile test of TMC in 45-degree direction
- Tensile test of Ti-6Al-4V

Elastic and plastic properties were estimated based on the test results. Compressive tests were also conducted to obtain the compressive strength.

2.3 Low-Velocity Impact Test

The drop-weight low-velocity impact tests were conducted using TMC specimens with 100mm length and 75 mm width. Experimental setup is shown in Fig. 3. A specimen was sandwiched by the fixture with 80mm \times 60mm rectangular hole, and was clamped by lightly tightening the bolts on the four corners of the fixture (Fig. 3). Impact load was applied to the specimens by the fall of the impactor with hemispherical tip, whose diameter was 15.9mm, at the center of the specimens. Sic fiber direction

Fig. 3 Drop-weight impact test apparatus of TMC

coincided with the longitudinal direction. Three levels of impact loading (impact energy of 20, 45, and 70 Joule) were applied to the TMC composites.

After the impact event, ultrasonic inspection using large-amplitude burst ultrasonic was performed to investigate the inner damage behavior of TMC composites. Some specimens were also cut to observe the damages by the optical microscope.

3 Experimental Results

3.1 Mechanical Properties

Basic engineering properties (e.g. Young’s moduli) are summarized in Table 1 for TMC and Table 2 for titanium clad layer. Plastic properties were evaluated by Hill and Mises yield functions for TMC and titanium, respectively.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of TMC

E_L (0-degree)	185 [GPa]
E_T (90-degree)	119 [GPa]
ν_{LT}	0.317
G_{LT}	46.4 [GPa]
Tensile Strength (0-degree)	1481 [MPa]
Tensile Strength (90-degree)	414 [MPa]
Shear Strength	220 [MPa]

Table 2 Mechanical properties of Ti-6Al-4V

E	126 [GPa]
ν	0.348
Tensile Strength	940 [MPa]

3.2 Impact Damage Behavior

During the impact test, reaction force of the impactor was recorded, and the corresponding acceleration and displacement of the impactor was calculated in the data acquisition system. The measured impact force-displacement curves corresponding to 20, 45, and 70 joules impacts to TMC composites with clad layers are summarized in Fig. 4. The impact damage behavior is also shown in Fig. 5 for TMC composites without clad layer subjected to 45 joules impact and in Fig. 6 for TMC composites with clad layers subjected to 45 joules

impact. Apparently, clad layers act as a role to prevent impact damages.

Fig. 4 Impact force-displacement curve of TMC composites with clad layers

Fig. 5 Impact damage of TMC without clad layer subjected to 45 joules impact

Fig. 6 Impact damage of TMC with clad layers subjected to 45 joules impact

Inner damages were also observed by ultrasonic inspection and optical microscope. Cross-sectional view of the TMC near the impact point is shown in Fig. 7. Fiber breakage and fiber/matrix debonding are observed. Ultrasonic inspection of the specimen corresponding to Fig. 5 is shown in Fig. 8, which

indicates inner damages expanding in the 90-degree direction.

Fig. 7 Cross-sectional view of the impacted TMC

Fig. 8 Ultrasonic image of TMC without clad layer subjected to 45 joules impact

4 Damage Simulation

4.1 Finite Element Modeling

When TMCs are subjected to impact loadings, yielding, fiber/matrix debonding, and fiber fracture occur in TMCs. Thus, yielding, strength-based damage onset, and stiffness degradation due to damages of TMC and titanium clad layers are incorporated in the finite element modeling using

MSC Marc software as described in our previous study [4]. TMC composites are treated as homogeneous anisotropic materials and discretized as solid elements.

Yield stresses and plastic hardening curves were determined based on the tensile test results. Hill and Mises yield functions were used for TMC and clad layers, respectively. The equivalent stress-equivalent plastic strain curve of TMC, and the corresponding input curve for FEM are shown in Fig. 9.

From the experimental observation, fiber breakage and fiber-matrix debonding are taken into account in the numerical simulation. Fiber breakage is modeled by tensile or compressive failure of homogeneous anisotropic material in fiber direction. Fiber-matrix debonding is considered as the material failure in the direction perpendicular to the fiber direction. In the present study, these failure onset conditions are simply expressed as

$$\left(\frac{1}{X_t} - \frac{1}{X_c}\right)\sigma_1 + \frac{\sigma_1^2}{X_t X_c} = 1 \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_2 = Y_t \quad (\sigma_2 > 0)$$

where X and Y denotes the strength in the fiber and perpendicular direction, and subscripts t and c express tension and compression, respectively. Subscripts 1 and 2 denotes the fiber and transverse directions.

Fig. 9 Equivalent plastic curve of TMC

For the clad layer, the following failure criterion is used to express different strength in tension and compression.

$$\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_t} - \frac{1}{\sigma_c}\right)\sigma_x + \frac{\sigma_x^2}{\sigma_t\sigma_c} + \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_t} - \frac{1}{\sigma_c}\right)\sigma_y + \frac{\sigma_y^2}{\sigma_t\sigma_c} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where σ_t and σ_c denotes the tensile and compressive strength of titanium.

Stiffness degradation owing to damage onset and accumulation is expressed by the stiffness reduction factor. This study utilizes a simple degradation rule; Young’s moduli and shear moduli of TMC and titanium are reduced to 1% of the original stiffnesses when the damage occurs.

4.2 Modeling of Low-Velocity Impact of TMC composites

Numerical simulation on the drop-weight impact tests of TMC composites is conducted herein. Low-velocity impact event is regarded as quasi-static indentation. In the actual impact tests, specimens were sandwiched by the fixtures, and were clamped by lightly tightening the bolts. Thus, thickness-wise displacements corresponding to the clamped area are constrained in the numerical simulation. The impactor is modeled as a stiff sphere. The corresponding FEM model (quarter model) is shown in Fig. 10. Indentation load is generated by applying the displacement in the thickness direction to the center of the sphere. When the applied indentation energy (i.e. sum of the product of applied displacement and reaction force) reaches 20, 45, or 70 joules, the prescribed displacement is reduced. Nonlinear static analysis was performed to simulate the damage growth in the low-velocity impact event.

Fig. 10 FEM model of drop-weight impact test.

4.3 Results of Low-Velocity Impact Damage

Load-displacement curves are compared between the simulation and experiment in the case of 45 joule low velocity impact of TMC composites with and without clad layers as shown in Fig. 11 and 12. The simulated damage area corresponding to Fig. 11 is also shown in Fig. 13, which can be compared with ultrasonic results of Fig. 8. The numerical simulation agrees well with the experimental results in terms of force-displacement curves and accumulated damage areas. The agreement could be confirmed in other loading cases and specimens with clad layers.

Fig. 11 Force-displacement curve of TMC without clad layer subject to 45 J impact

Fig. 12 Force-displacement curve of TMC with clad layers subject to 45 J impact

The present study aims to develop a relatively simple FEM model to simulate damage behavior of TMC. Anisotropic homogeneous elements considering plasticity, damage onset, and stiffness degradation are used for the damage behavior of unidirectional TMC composites. Although more sophisticated damage modeling would be possible, the present model gives accurate mechanical and

damage response of TMC. This model is expected to be useful for virtual testing of TMC structures.

Fig. 13 Comparison of the damage accumulation behavior between the simulation and the experiment (TMC without clad layer subjected to 45 joule impact)

4.4 High-Velocity Impact Simulation

Landing gear structures are susceptible to high-velocity impact (velocity is in the order of 100 m/s) by stones on the ground and birds during operation. In order to assess the safety of the TMC composite structures, it is necessary to investigate the damage behavior of TMC owing to not only the low-velocity impact but also the high-velocity impact.

The above-mentioned TMC model is used to simulate the damage behavior of TMC subjected to high-velocity impact. Using Marc software, dynamic analysis is performed to simulate the high-velocity impact damage of TMC.

TMC plates and boundary conditions are modeled in the same way described in the low-velocity impact simulation. The collision body is set to be a sphere of aluminum oxide (specific density is 3.6) with the diameter of 15 mm. Velocity is prescribed to the collision body of which damage is not considered.

Impact damage of two kinds of 100mm×75mm TMC panels is simulated; 2mm thickness TMC without clad layer and 2mm thickness TMC covered by 0.2mm clad layers. Simulated results of the impact force history and the accumulated damages are shown in Fig. 14 for the case of TMC panel and Fig. 15 for the case of TMC with clad layers.

(a) impact force history

(b) damage accumulation

Fig. 14 Damage accumulation of TMC panel without clad layer subjected to 100 m/s impact

(a) impact force history

(b) damage accumulation

Fig. 15 Damage accumulation of TMC panel with clad layers subjected to 100 m/s impact

For the validation of the high-velocity impact simulation, experimental investigation is also performed using TMC panels. High speed camera images of the high-velocity impact tests are presented in Fig. 16. The specimen apparatus after 100 m/s impact is shown in Fig. 17. As can be seen in Fig. 14, TMC plate without clad layer exhibits a longitudinal crack along the fibers, while experimental observation indicates complete longitudinal split of TMC as shown in Fig. 17. Although the damage behavior in the region constrained by the fixtures exhibits discrepancy between the simulation and the experiment, overall damage behavior in the general region can be well simulated. In the case of TMC with clad layers, apparent damage behavior is also comparable between the simulation and the experimental observation. Overall, it is concluded that the present simulation can capture the damage behavior of TMC plates subjected to foreign object impacts.

t = -0.667ms

t = 0ms

t = 0.972ms

Fig. 16 High speed camera images of the high-velocity impact test of TMC specimen with clad layers subjected to 100 m/s impact

(a) TMC (total 2mm thickness)

(b) TMC with clad layers (total 2.4mm thickness)

Fig. 17 Specimen apparatus after 100 m/s impact

5 Conclusion

In this paper, application of TMC is considered as a candidate material for landing gear structures of the aircraft. Mechanical properties of SiC fiber/titanium matrix composites were measured, and impact experiments of TMC were conducted to observe the foreign object impact damages in TMC. Numerical modeling to simulate the damage behavior of TMC was developed considering the plastic deformation and the damages, and mechanical response and damage behavior was compared with experimental results. Overall, the numerical model could predict damage behavior of TMC composites subjected to low-velocity and high-velocity impact loading. The developed model is expected to be useful for virtual testing of TMC structure.

References

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